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D3.1 Operations documentation on the Open Infrastructure deployment

Work Package 3. Pulsar Network: Distributed heterogeneous compute.

Technical References

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Executive Summary

Work Package 3 of the EuroScienceGateway project is divided into 5 tasks, aimed at bringing into production (TRL9) the Pulsar Network , a distributed computing network that allows public Galaxy servers to offload jobs to remote computing clusters provided by project partners.

Specifically, this deliverable describes the work done in tasks 3.1, 3.2, 3.3 and 3.5. The main objectives of WP3 are: 1) to simplify the deployment and management of new Pulsar and Galaxy endpoints (T3.1 and T3.5), to make Pulsar compatible with the GA4GH TES specifications (T3.2), and to deploy new Pulsar endpoints (T3.3)

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ARC	A dvanced R esource C onnector
CVMFS	C ERN V M F ile S ystem
ESG	E uro S cience G ateway (this project)
FAIR	F indable, A ccessible, I nteroperable, R eusable ¹ , a set of principles for scientific data management that emphasizes best practices and machine readability
GA4GH	G lobal A lliance for G enomics and H ealth
HPC	H igh P erformance C omputing
LRMS	L ocal R esource M anagement S ystem
NFS	N etwork F ile S ystem
OI	O pen I nfrastructure
TES	T ask E xecution S ervice
TESP	T ask E xecution S ervice to P ulsar
VGCN	V irtual G alaxy C ompute N odes
VM	V irtual M achine
WP	W ork P ackage

¹ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

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1. Introduction

This deliverable describes the operations performed for the development of the Open Infrastructure (more information in Section 2.3) and to build the European Pulsar Network (more details in Section 2).

National Cloud and HPC infrastructures have been typically established targeting local researchers, showing substantial differences in hardware, configurations, software stacks, authentication and authorization systems.

The goal of WP3 is to provide efficient and structured access to data, tools and workflows, exploiting the available IT infrastructures, to a vast plethora of (non necessarily local) users, in the most transparent way. At the same time, we seek to make available tools that empower users to establish and manage computational resources, thereby fostering the integration of new service providers.

In order to do so some key paradigms are necessary, as the adoption of open source software solutions, the federation of authentication systems, in such a way that there is no need for the partners to change the methods they are accustomed to, and the definition of automated (and documented) procedures for deploying and maintaining compute endpoints. Examples of the aforementioned technologies include (but are not limited to) OpenStack (as cloud management system), Terraform (to manage the resources using the infrastructure-as-code paradigm), Jenkins (for continuous integration and delivery), Ansible (for automatic configuration), and GitHub (to preserve code and make it publicly available).

From the users' point of view, the work carried out in WP3 enables user-friendly access to European compute and storage resources, and improve the availability of tools, workflows and reference data, by means of software tools such as Conda, Docker, Singularity (Apptainer), and CVMFS.

2. The European Pulsar Network

The European Pulsar Network (Fig. 1) is a distributed job execution system allowing to scale the computing resources available to Galaxy instances over heterogeneous and distributed compute facilities.

The ESG project foresees at least six national Galaxy instances linked to the Pulsar Network, with at least 10 Pulsar trusted endpoints, routing the incoming jobs from Galaxy and other workflow management systems to local compute resources. The number of compute endpoints can be easily extended using the Open Infrastructure, a set of tools developed to simplify the deployment of new ones, thus allowing to scale up the compute resources available to the Galaxy public servers. Finally, an activity aimed at enabling Nextflow and CWL job submission on the distributed computing network has started on M18 as a proof of concept and is currently ongoing.

Fig. 1 - The minimal coverage of Pulsar endpoints foreseen within the EuroScienceGateway project. The Galaxy logos indicate the 6 national Galaxy instances that will make use of the network at the end of the project.

2.1. Technical Background

Among the technical foundations of the European Pulsar Network the first to be cited is the workflow manager Galaxy², a user-friendly interface to workflows, tools, able to exploit compute and storage resources in a transparent way to end users, which is developed within the Galaxy project. Thanks to ESG, Galaxy is available with at least six UseGalaxy.* servers across Europe.

The Galaxy Project has developed a remote job execution system, based on the Pulsar application, which grants users access to compute infrastructures wherever they are available, regardless of their location and underlying architecture. It consists of a Python application server that accepts jobs from a remote Galaxy server and transfers them for execution to a local resource, fetching input data and then sending the results back to the remote Galaxy

² <https://galaxyproject.org/>

server after processing. Pulsar supports different workload management system, resource managers and HTC/HPC software frameworks, such as HTCondor³, SLURM⁴ and Kubernetes⁵.

The compute power available to the UseGalaxy servers can be also expanded through the Advanced Resource Connector⁶, a grid computing middleware adopted in research fields such as High Energy Physics. Like Pulsar, ARC allows the submission of computational tasks to different computing systems (e.g. HTCondor and SLURM), whose integration with Galaxy is under development within the Work Package 4.

Finally, the CernVM File System⁷ (CVMFS) is the underlying technology adopted for accessing and distributing tools, and reference data to computational endpoints. CVMFS is a software distribution service widely adopted for scientific computing environments, allowing efficient and reliable software deployment through a read-only HTTP-based protocol, supporting caching to minimize network load. This approach avoids wasteful data replication and provides easy access to consistent and up-to-date tools and data. In particular, the Galaxy Project CVMFS⁸ provides, among others, two repositories that are mounted on each compute endpoint:

- tools.galaxyproject.org which provides Apptainer containers, built from Conda packages, to solve tools dependencies.
- data.galaxyproject.org which provides reference data to tools, as for example genomic sequences and annotations for bioinformatics tools.

2.2. Architecture

The Pulsar Network architecture is shown in Fig. 2, where the European Galaxy server acts as the gateway for job submission. Indeed, while the default configuration of usegalaxy.eu allows it to submit jobs to the local HTCondor based cluster, it is also able to submit jobs to remote clusters belonging to the Pulsar Network.

Galaxy routes jobs to the suitable destination with the necessary computational resources using the Total Perspective Vortex (<https://total-perspective-vortex.readthedocs.io/>), which exploits a YAML file⁹ for destination mapping which includes the local cluster and remote Pulsar network nodes as well. When a job is scheduled to be executed in a pulsar endpoint, Galaxy appends a message on a RabbitMQ queue. Pulsar continuously monitors the queue, and when the message is found, input data are fetched from the Galaxy server, analysed

³ <https://htcondor.org/>

⁴ <https://slurm.schedmd.com/>

⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/>

⁶ <https://www.nordugrid.org/arc/>

⁷ <https://cernvm.cern.ch/fs/>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.1093/bioadv/vbac030>

⁹

<https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/infrastructure-playbook/blob/master/files/galaxy/tpv/destinations.yml#L2>

exploiting tools in the form of Apptainer containers instantiated from images pulled from the CVMFS, and then, on success, the results are uploaded back to Galaxy.

From the user's point of view, using a Pulsar endpoint currently means just selecting the endpoint in the proper menu under the user preferences section (developed within WP4).

Pulsar endpoints can be deployed on HPC or cloud e-infrastructures, since Pulsar is able to utilize various resource managers as compute backend, such as HPC ones managed by HTCondor, SLURM or Kubernetes, and/or remote cloud infrastructures deployed with the Open Infrastructure (see next section). Moreover, it is important to highlight that in principle any Galaxy server can access the Pulsar Network, provided the endpoints are properly configured to fetch its jobs. Currently, it is foreseen to open the access to all usegalaxy.* servers belonging to the ESG consortium.

Fig. 2 - The Pulsar Network architecture. The European Galaxy server is used as the access point to the network for job submission. Jobs can be submitted to the local compute (HTCondor based) infrastructure, or to the Pulsar Network available endpoints. These endpoints can be deployed either on HPC or cloud e-infrastructures, using different resource managers.

2.3. The Open Infrastructure

The Open infrastructure (OI) is a set of open source tools able to deploy and maintain ready-to-use Pulsar endpoints and Galaxy servers. Its aim is to enable ESG Consortium partners and, more in general, service providers, to deploy new Pulsar nodes to extend the computing capacity of the network and/or new Galaxy public servers to exploit the network computing power.

The OI encompasses the following instruments:

- A virtual machine image, named Virtual Galaxy Compute Node (<https://usegalaxy.eu/static/vgcn/>), providing pre-installed tools needed to run Galaxy jobs. The image includes the Pulsar application, Apptainer and Docker engines for Galaxy tools dependency resolution, the CVMFS client for mounting the Galaxy CVMFS repository, providing tools and reference data, NFS server and client, and Telegraf¹⁰ for metrics collection.
- The CERN VM FileSystem is a read-only network file system optimized for delivering software and scientific data to globally distributed computing environments. It is used to provide Apptainer containers and Reference data to Galaxy tools.
- Hashicorp Terraform¹¹ allows users to define and create virtual infrastructures across multiple cloud providers. The OI provides all needed terraform files for configuring and deploying compute, network and storage services to build a Pulsar endpoint.
- Ansible¹² is an automation engine that automates the installation and configuration of applications by using an infrastructure as code paradigm. It uses simple YAML syntax for its playbooks, enabling efficient automation with minimal learning curve. The OI exploits Ansible to perform Pulsar and/or Galaxy configuration and update routines.

Terraform and Ansible recipes are hosted on the Pulsar Deployment Github repository¹³, allowing users to automatically deploy, install and configure a HTCondor cluster, with NFS among compute nodes, turning on the Pulsar application for fetching jobs from Galaxy. Each endpoint uses Apptainer and the Galaxy CVMFS repository as default choice for dependency resolution, which are able to provide containerised tools for each Galaxy wrapper.

The Pulsar endpoint deployment recipes have been reworked and continuously updated, reflecting upstream tools updates. In particular:

- The VGCN image has been update to RockyLinux 9,
- Pulsar has been updated to version 0.15.6,
- HTCondor has been updated to version 10.X, with new authentication mechanism among compute nodes and Central Manager,
- Ansible roles and Terraform recipes have been updated reflecting previous changes.

¹⁰ <https://www.influxdata.com/time-series-platform/telegraf/>

¹¹ <https://www.terraform.io/>

¹² <https://www.ansible.com/>

¹³ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/pulsar-deployment>

A step-by-step tutorial for the deployment of a Pulsar endpoint is given in the Pulsar Network documentation¹⁴.

Currently, OpenStack access to a dedicated project and Galaxy rabbitMQ credentials are the only requirements needed to perform the endpoint creation, with just a single command:

```
terraform apply -var "pvt_key=~/.ssh/<key>" -var
"condor_pass=<condor-password>" -var
"mq_string=pyamqp://<pulsar>:<password>@mq.galaxyproject.eu:5671//pulsar
/<pulsar>?ssl=1"
```

The command requires:

- a public SSH key needed to connect to the created VMs;
- a password for the HTCondor Cluster, used for compute nodes / central manager connection;
- RabbitMQ credentials to contact Galaxy and fetch jobs.

The Fig. 3 shows the deployment of a Pulsar Endpoint at CINECA AdaCloud in Italy.

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Actions
vgnbwc-worker-test-8872	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.228	fl.ada.xs	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months	Create Snapshot
vgnbwc-worker-test-0740	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.148	fl.ada.xs	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.backup	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.14	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months, 4 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.replica	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.204	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months, 4 weeks	Create Snapshot
jenkins-bridge-wn	Ubuntu Server 20.04 LTS (Focal Fossa)	192.168.0.248, 131.175.205.30	fl.ada.xs	mtangaro-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months	Create Snapshot
i02-exec-node-0-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.252	fl.ada.m	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
i02-central-manager-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.152, 131.175.205.137	fl.ada.xs	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
i02-nfs-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.189	fl.ada.xs	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy-ft-exec-test	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.87	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.condor-nfs	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.249	fl.ada.m	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.galaxy	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.169, 131.175.207.122	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.rabbitmq	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.124, 131.175.207.49	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.condor-central-manager	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.98, 131.175.207.129	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.database	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.90	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot

Fig. 3 - Pulsar deployment (IT02) at CINECA AdaCloud infrastructure. The endpoint encompasses a HTCondor Central Manager, one compute node and a NFS server providing the storage to the whole cluster.

¹⁴ <https://pulsar-network.readthedocs.io>

The Open Infrastructure also encompasses all instruments for deploying and maintaining Galaxy production servers, providing also a robust framework for maintaining and updating running instances. The documentation for using all recipes for creating a full fledged usegalaxy.eu replica server, used for building the Italian UseGalaxy instance is available at <https://usegalaxy-it.github.io/documentation>.

Terraform is used to deploy a set of virtual machines, allocated with different resources (CPU, RAM, storage) and network settings, each of which will host a different Galaxy service. Terraform recipes are available in the infrastructure repository of usegalaxy.eu, using RockyLinux 9 as the base image for each VM. Indeed, the recipes have been successfully used to deploy the UseGalaxy.it server¹⁵.

Instance Name	Image Name	IP Address	Flavor	Key Pair	Status	Availability Zone	Task	Power State	Age	Actions
vgnbwc-worker-test-5872	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.226	fl.ada.xs	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months	Create Snapshot
vgnbwc-worker-test-0740	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.148	fl.ada.xs	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.backup	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.14	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months, 4 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.replica	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64.qcow2-DB_test	192.168.0.204	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	3 months, 4 weeks	Create Snapshot
jenkins-bridge-wn	Ubuntu Server 20.04 LTS (Focal Fossa)	192.168.0.248, 131.175.205.30	fl.ada.xs	mtangaro-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months	Create Snapshot
i02-exec-node-0-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.252	fl.ada.m	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
i02-central-manager-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.152, 131.175.205.137	fl.ada.xs	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
i02-nfs-usegalaxy.eu	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.189	fl.ada.xs	i02-pulsar-key	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 1 week	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.it-exec-test	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.87	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	4 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.condor-nfs	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.249	fl.ada.m	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.galaxy	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.169, 131.175.207.122	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.rabbitmq	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.124, 131.175.207.49	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.condor-central-manager	vggp-v60-j225-1a1d01ec8f3-dev	192.168.0.98, 131.175.207.129	fl.ada.s	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot
usegalaxy.database	Rocky-9-GeneriCloud.latest.x86_64	192.168.0.90	fl.ada.l	cloud	Active	eu-nova	None	Running	5 months, 3 weeks	Create Snapshot

Fig. 4 - UseGalaxy.it test deployment at CINECA AdaCloud infrastructure. Each service is installed on a different VM. The number of compute nodes available to the HTCondor cluster are increased depending on the job workload.

The Fig. 4 shows the UseGalaxy.it test deployment at the CINECA AdaCloud infrastructure. The minimal setup encompasses::

1. 1 VM for Galaxy and its its companion services, e.g. Nginx;
2. 3 VM for PostgreSQL, including a replica and a backup server;
3. 1 VM used as NFS server, with storage space exported to the whole deployment;
4. 1 VM for the RabbitMQ server;
5. a HTCondor cluster responsible to provide the compute resources needed by Galaxy.

¹⁵ UseGalaxy.it infrastructure repository: <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it/infrastructure>, and deployment information: <https://usegalaxy-it.github.io/documentation/deployment.html>.

Ansible is then used to configure the created infrastructure. All needed playbooks used to create and manage the usegalaxy.eu server are available at <https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/infrastructure-playbook>. Playbooks are available to:

- perform PostgreSQL installation, with replica and Backup;
- setup the RabbitMQ message broker which is used to exchange messages between Galaxy server and Pulsar endpoints;
- solve software dependencies and setup the “galaxy” user for operations
- install and configure HTCondor on the corresponding nodes;
- install and configure nginx and gxdm, which is useful for galaxy administration tasks;
- install galaxy and TUSd.

Finally, recipes for other components, like the Grafana dashboard or the TlaaS¹⁶ are also available.

We also highlight that every Galaxy installation step, the ansible roles and their variables, have been documented in the “Galaxy installation with Ansible” tutorial available in the Galaxy Training Network¹⁷.

3. Pulsar endpoints

Currently the European Pulsar Network encompasses 11 endpoints (Fig. 5 and Table 1), created by the consortium partner, using the pulsar deployment repository. Moreover, one endpoint has been added by the HCMR institute¹⁸ for the FairEase¹⁹ ([Pull Request](#)) project: it has been tested with their tools and will be used for testing the new tools developed within the project.

¹⁶ <https://usegalaxy-eu.github.io/tlaas.html>

¹⁷ <https://training.galaxyproject.org/training-material/topics/admin/tutorials/ansible-galaxy/tutorial.html>

¹⁸ <https://www.hcmr.gr/en/>

¹⁹ <https://fairease.eu/>

Institution	Country	Endpoint name
ALU-FR	Germany	DE01
CNR	Italy	IT01, IT02 and IT03*
CNRS	France	FR01
IISAS	Slovakia	SK01
CESNET	Czech Republic	CZ01
VIB	Belgium	BE01
EGI and INFN	Italy	EGI01
BSC	Spain	BSC01
TUBITAK ULAKBIM	Turkey	TUBITAK01
Cyfronet	Poland	CFY01
FairEase project	Greece	HCMR01

Table. 1 - European Pulsar Network endpoints. (*) IT03 is currently connected for testing to UseGalaxy.it).

Fig. 5 - Pulsar endpoints distribution among consortium partners.

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4. UseGalaxy.* instances

Currently, 7 UseGalaxy endpoints are available from the project's partners: usegalaxy.eu (ALU-FR), usegalaxy.be (VIB), usegalaxy.fr (CNRS), usegalaxy.es (BSC-CNS), usegalaxy.no (ELIXIR-NO), usegalaxy.cz (CESNET), and usegalaxy.it (CNR).

The activities focused mainly on the management and maintenance of the instances:

- aligning to Galaxy 23.0 or later release;
- switching to Total Perspective Vortex dynamic job destination tool²⁰;
- integrating Pulsar endpoints;
- updating OS image to RockyLinux 9 (or Ubuntu or Almalinux 8) and PostgreSQL versions;
- Aligning on the adoption of the same set of Ansible recipes from the GalaxyProject community.

In the following we summarize the activities carried out by UseGalaxy.* national teams to maintain and update the servers.

²⁰ <https://arxiv.org/abs/2312.02060>

4.1. *The European Galaxy server UseGalaxy.eu*

We have made several important updates to UseGalaxy.eu to keep it running smoothly and efficiently. We've updated Galaxy to the latest version, 24.1, following previous upgrades to versions 24.0 and 23.1. This ensures we use the latest features and improvements in the Galaxy platform. We've also created new Rocky Linux 9 OS images for our compute cluster, TaaS (Training Infrastructure as a Service), and Pulsar endpoints. Along with this upgrade, we updated Pulsar to version 0.15.6 and HTCondor to version 10, among other updates. These changes help keep our systems secure and up-to-date. We migrated from OpenStack Train to Zed, as a result, we redeployed all our Galaxy services, including Rustus (upload service), Apollo (genome annotation), Celery (task queue), Plausible (analytics), FTP, and the TIG stack (Telegraf, InfluxDB, Grafana), and the compute infrastructure to the new cloud environment.

We have onboarded new Pulsar endpoints and subcommunities and updated Grafana to version 11.0.0, migrating from SQLite to PostgreSQL as config backend. This migration enhances our infrastructure and services monitoring and stability, providing a more robust backend for our analytics. We also automated the export of Grafana dashboards to a public GitHub repository (<https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/grafana-dashboards>), making it easy for the community to reuse them.

To improve availability and load balancing, we implemented Traefik Reverse Proxy (<https://galaxyproject.org/news/2024-07-17-traefik/>). Traefik allows us to have two head nodes for UseGalaxy.eu, which helps reduce downtime during maintenance. This setup also enables us to test new features without interrupting users by directing a subset of traffic to a second Galaxy server. Additionally, Traefik handles SSL certificates automatically, simplifying secure connections and certificate management. This setup is crucial for maintaining a smooth operation, especially with over 100,000 registered users. Further, we have integrated Plausible for monitoring analytics, providing insights into user interactions while respecting their privacy. Plausible helps us improve our services based on user behavior, ensuring we cater to the needs of our community efficiently.

For better security, we disabled older TLS versions and now support only TLS v1.3 and v1.2 for our MQ server. We optimized our PostgreSQL server to handle the demands of over 100,000 users more efficiently. We added an Invenio RDM file source, allowing users to manage their research data directly within UseGalaxy.eu. We also expanded our login options by integrating EGI Check-in, offering Single Sign-On (SSO) alongside EOSC Life Science and Dataplant logins.

To protect our services, we implemented a new malware detection tool called WALL-E²¹. While free and publicly available resources lower barriers to science, they attract not only legitimate users. This is especially true for environments with more freedom, like privileged command line access and the ability to install packages and execute arbitrary code. WALL-E scans for malicious jobs using signature techniques, optimized by CRC-32 and validated by SHA-1 to reduce false positives. It targets abuse like cryptocurrency mining, which we've seen since 2021. The tool is easy to deploy with Ansible and uses community-contributed signatures from a public GitHub repository.

Finally, with the release of Galaxy 24.1, we introduced the "Bring Your Own Storage" (BYOS) and "Bring Your Own Data" (BYOD) features. BYOS allows users to connect any cloud or on-premises storage solution to Galaxy, greatly expanding their storage options. BYOD lets users add their own data sources to Galaxy, providing more flexibility in data management. These features empower users by leveraging external storage resources and data sources, ensuring they have the capacity and flexibility they need for their research.

4.2. *UseGalaxy.fr (France)*

The French UseGalaxy server was initially created in 2019, but ESG allowed to make significant improvements to it. This instance is installed on the infrastructure of the French Institute of bioinformatics (IFB, ELIXIR French node), with access to a shared Slurm cluster with 8400 cores, 52 Tb of RAM, 4 Pb of storage, and 6 GPU cards.

The instance is installed on 4 Ubuntu 20.04 VMs (Galaxy, database, Nginx proxy and monitoring). Three deployment environments have been set up: a development one (allowing to make manual tweaking and tests), a preproduction one (to validate each change), and a production one which is the one available to all users on UseGalaxy.fr. Configuration and deployment is performed using Ansible playbooks using the standard roles maintained by the Galaxy community. These playbooks are available on IFB's GitLab repositories²² and the deployment process is automated using GitLab's CI/CD mechanism.

Using this infrastructure, the server has been successively upgraded to reach the 24.0 version, and several features were implemented: dynamic job destinations with Total Perspective Vortex, TlaaS for training, 8 domain-centric subdomains, interactive tools (like RStudio or Jupyter) and CVMFS for reference data and dependency resolution.

In addition to UseGalaxy.fr, a French Pulsar node (FR01) has been deployed on GenOuest's OpenStack. It has been deployed using the Terraform and Ansible roles developed in the context of ESG, and is already offering computing resources to UseGalaxy.eu users, and soon to the other national instances.

²¹ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-eu/WallE>

²² <https://gitlab.com/ifb-elixirfr/usegalaxy-fr/>

The UseGalaxy.fr server has currently more than 6500 user accounts and 4.5 million jobs since its opening.

4.3. *UseGalaxy.it (Italy)*

The Italian UseGalaxy server is currently under development as part of the ESG project, with CNR as the lead institution, and INFN (also a beneficiary of ESG), CINECA, and GARR providing compute and storage resources.

At present, the test server has been deployed on the CINECA's AdaCloud facility, utilizing exclusively cloud resources through Terraform and Ansible configurations provided by ESG. The server has been created using Terraform recipes²³ (see Fig. 4), which created a VM for each Galaxy service, including the one providing HTCondor. Then, all services have been installed and configured using Ansible playbooks²⁴. Finally, server management is supported by a CI/CD Jenkins server²⁵ and integrated with GitHub. This allows the extension of the HTCondor Cluster on-demand, just by modifying the resource file²⁶ on GitHub, which describes the computational resources assigned to the cluster.

To enhance the server's resources and leverage the resources of all the technological partners of ELIXIR Italy that can host Pulsar endpoints, we have established connections to the Pulsar Network at GARR Cloud, ADA Cloud (Cineca), and the ReCaS Bari datacenter. The Pulsar endpoint IT03, deployed at GARR Cloud, is currently connected with usegalaxy.it for testing and works correctly.

The deployment procedures and all the configuration have been reported in the documentation²⁷, in order to ensure the possibility to rebuild the server if needed.

4.4. *UseGalaxy.be (Belgium)*

The Belgian UseGalaxy server was first created in 2019 and is hosted on the OpenStack environment provided by The Flemish Supercomputer Center (Vlaams Supercomputer Centrum - VSC). As part of ESG we have been able to make significant improvements to our deployment.

The Galaxy server is set up across four RockyLinux 9 VMs (Galaxy, Nginx Proxy, Database and NFS) and a HTCondor cluster consisting of 7 nodes with 1.74TB of RAM and 120 CPU cores. Two deployment environments are set up: a production - and a test environment (mainly for testing of upgrades). All VMs are deployed using Terraform and Ansible configurations provided by ESG and are currently stored in private Github repositories.

²³ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it/infrastructure>

²⁴ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it/infrastructure-playbook>

²⁵ <https://build-usegalaxy-it.cloud.ba.infn.it/jenkins>

²⁶ <https://github.com/usegalaxy-it/vgcn-infrastructure/blob/master/resources.yaml>

²⁷ <https://usegalaxy-it.github.io/documentation/>

The Galaxy server was upgraded to 23.0 during the course of ESG, so far, and is currently being prepared to be upgraded to 24.1. Features that have been made available during this time include: dynamic job scheduling using Total Perspective Vortex and TlaaS for training. In addition to UseGalax.be, a Belgian Pulsar node (BE01) has been deployed on the same OpenStack. It has been deployed using the Terraform and Ansible roles developed in the context of ESG, and is already offering computing resources to UseGalaxy.eu users, and soon to the other national instances.

4.5. *UseGalaxy.cz (Czech Republic)*

The Czech UseGalaxy installation is in a ready-for-production state. It consists of the Galaxy server and a dedicated Pulsar server, both hosted in the fault-tolerant CESNET VMWare cloud²⁸. Pulsar submits jobs to dedicated queues of the shared e-Infra CZ environment²⁹; through settings of those queues the resources available to the Galaxy jobs can be regulated dynamically (currently 10 nodes with 32 CPU cores and 192 GB RAM are allocated). Several GPU nodes are also available, with specific compute node configurations for Alphafold jobs (64 CPU cores, 512 GB RAM, 4x nVidia A40).

The services are deployed with ansible recipes inherited from ESG³⁰, and they are being cleaned up and refactored to support full Github CI/CD.

4.6. *UseGalaxy.no (Norway)*

We have got more people to the usegalaxy.no team and they are currently focusing on migrating usegalaxy.no servers to almalinux 8. Currently we are running our usegalaxy.no production stack on a dedicated hypervisor. We have plans to move this to Openstack provided by NREC³¹ (Norwegian Research and Education Cloud) in the future. Our compute cluster consists of 5 static vm's having a total compute capacity of 148 cores and 822Gb of memory. The UseGalaxy.no server was upgraded 3 releases on April 2nd (v22.01, v22.05 and v23.0) and then 2 more releases on April 3rd (v23.1 and v23.2).

The usegalaxy.no servers are also scanned for security vulnerabilities using Nessus vulnerability scanner that are generating a report to us every week. We have taken actions according to this report.

²⁸ <https://virtualizace.cesnet.cz/>

²⁹ <https://metacentrum.cz>

³⁰ <https://github.org/CESNET/usegalaxy> and https://github.org/CESNET/pulsar_node

³¹ <https://nrec.no/>

4.7. UseGalaxy.es (Spain)

The UseGalaxy platform instance in Spain (found at usegalaxy.es) has recently been migrated to a new OpenStack-based cloud server, using Ubuntu 22.04 machines. Our compute cluster currently consists of 48 vCPUs and 128 GB RAM, and could be expanded in the future. Before the migration, usegalaxy.es was updated twice, first to version 21.0 and then to version 22.0. With the latest migration, the platform has been upgraded to Galaxy version 23.0, and a future update is planned to stay aligned with usegalaxy.eu.

This migration to the new Openstack cloud is also being carried out for the Pulsar node (ES01), having to update the virtual machine that hosted it to avoid version problems. All these developments are being recorded and made into ansible playbooks for easier future implementations and will be made available through gitlab when the implementation is complete.

5. GA4GH Task Execution Service (TES) support in Pulsar

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) is a worldwide organization which aims to speed up the ethical exchange of genomic and health data to enhance research, improve clinical care, and support personalized medicine. In particular, The Task Execution Service specification³², is a standard developed by the GA4GH for orchestrating complex genomic analyses, exploiting several (cloud-based) computing environments. TES simplifies the workflows' orchestration, abstracting the underlying infrastructure, making large-scale data processing more accessible and efficient.

The TESP (TES to Pulsar) component³³, implemented in T3.2, provides the standardized GA4GH TES interface³⁴ on top of Pulsar. The TES endpoint, which becomes exposed at the Pulsar site, is authenticated with OAuth³⁵, and virtually any authorization rule can be applied based on the authentication. Internally, TESP maps its API calls to the corresponding calls of Pulsar REST interface (which is used internally only, and it does not need to be exposed), fully leveraging the Pulsar abstraction of batch systems.

The use of TESP in Galaxy was demonstrated with an extended Galaxy TES job runner³⁶. The implementation also optimizes input and output dataset transfers – according to the TES specification, the job runner provides URLs to download/upload the datasets, and TESP translates these to prologue/epilogue code of the job script (wrapping the actual Galaxy tool), ensuring that no unnecessary copying the data happens³⁷.

³² <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/task-execution-service-tes/>

³³ <https://github.com/CESNET/tesp-api>

³⁴ <https://www.ga4gh.org/product/task-execution-service-tes/>

³⁵ <https://oauth.net/2/>

³⁶ <https://github.com/CESNET/usegalaxy/blob/galaxy-umsa/files/galaxy/tes.py>

³⁷ Described in more detail in Galaxy conference contribution, [10.7490/f1000research.1119817.1](https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119817.1)

6. *Summary and conclusions*

This deliverable outlines the activities carried out within the Work Package 3 of EuroScienceGateway for the development of the Pulsar Network. This Work Package addresses two fundamental aspects of the project: the creation of a software framework (the Open Infrastructure) that assists administrators and service providers in establishing new endpoints and managing large-scale Galaxy servers; and the creation of a network of endpoints to be made available to existing servers.

The documentation for the use of the Open Infrastructure has been published and is constantly updated to reflect the changes made in the OI software. The procedure for deploying new endpoints has been reviewed, and new endpoints can be now deployed and managed more easily. To date, the network includes 12 Pulsar endpoints and 7 national Galaxy instances.

